

1 Europe will struggle to meet the new WHO Air Quality Guidelines

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12 Abstract

13
14 The World Health Organization (WHO) updated its Global Air Quality Guidelines in 2021 due
15 to growing evidence on adverse health impacts of air pollution even at low concentrations. We
16 used a suite of regional atmospheric chemistry models to simulate fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5})
17 and ozone (O₃) levels over Europe in 2015-2050 and assessed the compliance of European
18 countries with the new guidelines under different emission scenarios. The results show that 65%
19 of the EU countries will comply with the PM_{2.5} target value (5 µg m⁻³) by 2050 under ambitious
20 emission reductions (SSP1-2.6). Under less ambitious mitigation scenarios (SSP2-4.5 and SSP3-
21 7.0), the compliance level is only 10%. In addition, none of the EU countries will comply with
22 the O₃ target value (60 µg m⁻³), while interim values are achieved in most of the EU countries,
23 partly under SSP2-4.5, and to a large extent under SSP1-2.6. These results highlight that
24 reaching the new WHO limit values will be challenging for Europe, partly due to natural
25 contribution to PM_{2.5} reaching up to 50% in some regions. Our findings imply the necessity of
26 more drastic emission reductions to meet the targets.
27

28 1. Introduction

29 Fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and ozone (O₃) are associated with a range of negative health
30 outcomes, including premature mortality, with large economic impacts on society [1-3]. The
31 existing estimates of global premature mortality vary substantially, typically differing by a factor
32 of about two. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated 4.2 million premature deaths in
33 2016, globally [1]. In contrast, Im et al. [3] and Lelieveld et al. [4] estimated higher figures of 5.3
34 million and 8.8. million in 2015, respectively, related to exposure to PM_{2.5} and O₃. In Europe,
35 specifically, the number of premature deaths has been estimated to be around 300 to 800
36 thousand [2,4]. Recently, Achebak et al. [5] estimated 115 thousand as the O₃-related premature
37 mortality in 2015-2017. According to the European Environment Agency (EEA), exposure to
38 PM_{2.5} was responsible for approximately 250 thousand premature deaths in 2023 in the EU

39 countries, marking a reduction of 45% between 2005 and 2022 [6,7]. The differences in these
40 assessments stem from different exposure-response functions used across studies, and
41 differences in methodology of exposure calculations [8]. In particular, the upper estimate of
42 Lelieveld et al. [4] is based on post-processed simulations of global atmospheric models with
43 coarse resolutions and/or limited chemistry representations as well as accounting for all non-
44 communicable diseases [9].

45 Due to a growing body of evidence on the health impacts of air pollution ([10]:
46 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/special-issue/10MTC4W8FXJ> and references therein) even at
47 lower concentrations than previously understood [11-14], the World Health Organization (WHO)
48 updated its 2005 Global Air Quality Guidelines in September 2021 [1]. The new air quality
49 guidelines are ambitious and recommend limit values for six air pollutants: PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃,
50 nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂). These guidelines are
51 not legally binding but can potentially influence air quality policy across the globe in the near-
52 mid-term future. Among these pollutants, annual mean concentration of PM_{2.5} is recommended
53 not to exceed 5 µg m⁻³, while the 99th percentile of daily mean PM_{2.5} is recommended not to
54 exceed 15 µg m⁻³. The guidelines for O₃ set the short-term exposure to (annual 99th percentile
55 of daily maximum 8-hourly surface O₃ (DMAX8hrO₃) concentration) not to exceed 100 µg m⁻³,
56 and the long-term exposure guideline recommends a peak season mean DMAX8hrO₃ of 60 µg
57 m⁻³. Following these developments, the European Parliament published the new EU directive on
58 air quality, which entered into force in December 2024. The new directive is an ambitious
59 roadmap to the EU Zero Pollution Action Plan towards 2050, when air pollution is reduced to
60 levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems.

61 The available literature on compliance to these new air quality guidelines are mainly limited to
62 measurements or modeling studies focusing on the present-day, while we are not aware of any
63 studies estimating if and when different regions or countries will comply in the future. According
64 to EEA [15], more than 90% of the European monitoring stations registered PM_{2.5} and O₃
65 concentrations above the WHO annual guideline levels in 2022. Bowdalo et al. [16] compared
66 the new WHO limit values with ground station observations across Europe and found that the
67 target levels are widely exceeded, with up to 98% of stations exceeding the annual PM_{2.5}
68 guideline level of 5 µg m⁻³. Franke et al. [17] showed that in Europe, PM_{2.5} concentrations in
69 2016 exceed the annual WHO guideline levels more than a factor of 5 and O₃ by up to a factor of
70 2, and that the mortality attributable to air pollution can be reduced by up to 70% depending on
71 the emission scenario.

72 The present study therefore aims to project the future PM_{2.5} and O₃ levels over Europe and the
73 individual EU countries until 2050 under different emission scenarios using a multi-model
74 ensemble and assess if and when the new WHO guidelines will be achieved across Europe.

75 **2 Results and Discussion**

76
77 2.1. Compliance to WHO PM_{2.5} interim and limit values
78

79 The analysis has been performed for the bias-corrected simulated annual mean PM_{2.5} surface
80 concentrations (see Methods section 7) to alleviate the impact of models underestimating surface
81 PM_{2.5} concentrations by -4% to -57%, with a bias of -24% for the multi-model mean (MMM;
82 Table 1). As the bias correction has been done using monthly observed PM_{2.5} values (see
83 Methods section 6), we have not performed analyses on the 99th percentile of the daily mean
84 PM_{2.5} concentrations. Figure 1 shows the surface PM_{2.5} concentrations over continental Europe
85 as simulated by the MMM under the different scenarios, after bias-correction. Surface PM_{2.5}
86 concentrations decrease from 2015 to 2050 in all three scenarios, by 47%, 26%, and 13% under
87 SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP3-7.0, respectively. The largest decreases are projected to take
88 place over central Europe, in particular under SSP1-2.6 (Figure 2, upper panel). However, as
89 seen in Figure 1, SSP1-2.6 is the only scenario where the mean surface PM_{2.5} concentration
90 approaches the 5 µg m⁻³ WHO target value, only after 2040, and only according to some models.
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93
94 Figure 1. Bias-corrected surface PM_{2.5} concentrations as predicted by the ensemble mean in
95 2015-2050 over continental Europe under different emission scenarios (solid lines of the
96 corresponding color). The black line shows the WHO guidelines target value of 5 µg m⁻³. Shaded
97 ranges show the standard deviation between the individual models.
98

99
 100 Figure 2. PM_{2.5} (upper panel) and O₃ (lower panel) surface concentrations in 2050 with respect to
 101 2015 under different emissions scenarios: SSP3-7.0 (left panel), SSP2-4.5 (middle panel), and
 102 SSP1-2.6 (right panel).

103
 104 Figure 3 shows if and when the future surface PM_{2.5} concentrations in the individual EU
 105 countries are projected to comply with the WHO guidelines under the different emission
 106 scenarios, based on the MMM. As seen in the figure, the majority of the EU countries are
 107 projected to not fulfill the WHO target value of $5 \mu g m^{-3}$ for PM_{2.5}. According to the MMM, 19
 108 countries, mainly western and northern countries will comply with the WHO target level under
 109 the SSP1-2.6 scenario, and majority only after 2030 or 2040. Few countries in Scandinavia
 110 (Finland, Norway, and Sweden) also comply in the SSP2-4.5 and SSP3-7.0 scenarios, already
 111 during present-day.

112
 113 Compliance to the interim values (Figure 3) is easier. The first interim value of $35 \mu g m^{-3}$ is
 114 complied with in all EU countries and is therefore not shown in Figure 3. All EU countries
 115 would have already complied with the interim target 3 ($15 \mu g m^{-3}$) if the developments during
 116 2015-2024 would follow SSP1-2.6 or SSP2-4.5, and only two countries (Bulgaria and Cyprus)
 117 would not comply under SSP3-7.0. Similarly, all EU countries either already or will comply with
 118 interim target 4 ($10 \mu g m^{-3}$) under SSP1-2.6, the majority before 2025, while Bulgaria and
 119 Cyprus will not comply in SSP2-4.5. Under SSP3-7.0, the majority of countries complies with
 120 the interim target 4, while 12 countries will fail reaching $10 \mu g m^{-3}$. Overall, results show that

121 compliance to WHO target and interim values for PM_{2.5} will mainly be possible after 2040, and
 122 mostly in the western and northern Europe.
 123

124
 125 Figure 3. WHO interim and target values for surface PM_{2.5} and the compliance across
 126 European countries under SSP1-2.6 (right panel), SSP2-4.5 (middle panel), and SSP3-7.0 (left
 127 panel).

128
 129 2.2. Contribution of natural sources to PM_{2.5} concentrations

130
 131 Two of the models from our ensemble, SILAM and WRF-Chem, have the natural emission of
 132 mineral dust aerosols calculated online (see Methods section 4). Current version of the DEHM
 133 model has natural mineral dust from the boundaries only and has no natural mineral dust
 134 emissions. Although all three models have online-calculated sea-salt aerosols, due to missing
 135 natural mineral dust emissions in the DEHM model, we estimated the contribution of natural
 136 aerosols (mineral dust and sea-salt) only with the SILAM and WRF-Chem models.

137
 138 Contribution of mineral dust and sea-salt to domain-mean PM_{2.5} mass accounts for around 27%
 139 in SILAM (Figure 4: top left panel) and around 37% in WRF-Chem (Figure 4: top right panel) in
 140 the present day. The contributions in 2015 over the continental Europe are upwards of 20% in
 141 SILAM, largest around the coastal areas in the north and western regions due to sea-salt aerosols,
 142 and in the Mediterranean also due to mineral dust (Figure 4, lower left panel). Same pattern is
 143 modelled by the WRF-Chem model (Figure 4, lower right panel), however with the contributions
 144 up to 50%, particularly over Scandinavia and the northwestern coast. Differences are linked to
 145 the different dust and sea-salt parameterizations in the two models (see Methods section 4).
 146 These contributions are comparable with available literature, reporting up to 16% natural
 147 contribution in southern Europe [18,19]. Gu et al. [20] attributed up to 20% of PM_{2.5}-related
 148 premature mortality in Europe during 2005-2015 to natural sources. Im et al. [21] estimated more

149 than 30% of sea-salt contribution to surface $PM_{2.5}$ in the Nordic region. Both models predict that
 150 the relative contribution due to natural sources increases in the future, and the rate of increase
 151 depends on how significantly the anthropogenic $PM_{2.5}$ is mitigated; SSP1-2.6 leads to the largest
 152 increase in the natural contribution while SSP3-7.0 leads to the smallest increase. This large
 153 contribution, which can be spatially up to 50% in SILAM and 70% in WRF-Chem, shows the
 154 challenge in parts of Europe to reach the WHO target value of $5 \mu g m^{-3}$ in the future. This
 155 contribution can grow even larger if other natural contributions, such as biogenic secondary
 156 organic aerosols, are singled out from secondary aerosols. Figure 4 also shows that in 2015,
 157 surface $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations over the continental Europe, except for northern Scandinavia, are
 158 above $5 \mu g m^{-3}$. Regions with $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations above $5 \mu g m^{-3}$ decrease in the future, largest
 159 in the SSP1-2.6 scenario (Figure S4). The exceedances remain in all scenarios over regions
 160 ,which are largely affected by natural $PM_{2.5}$; in particular over the coastal areas, as well as over
 161 southern Europe, which is largely affected by dust transport.

162

163

164 Figure 4. Primary natural (mineral dust and sea-salt) contribution (%) to domain-mean $PM_{2.5}$
 165 mass over Europe in SILAM (upper left panel) and WRF-Chem (upper right panel) under

166 different SSP scenarios (shaded areas represent the spatial variability). Lower panels show 2015
167 annual mean of the dust + sea-salt contribution (%) to PM_{2.5} under SSP2-4.5 scenario for SILAM
168 (left) and WRF-Chem (right). The dot-shaded regions are where PM_{2.5} concentrations are above
169 5 µg m⁻³.

170

171 2.3. Compliance to WHO O₃ interim and limit values

172

173 Peak season DMAX8hrO₃ averaged over the EU countries as simulated by the MMM are
174 presented in Figure 5, along with the WHO target value of 60 µg m⁻³. The bias correction is not
175 applied over the simulated O₃ concentrations, as the normalized mean bias (*NMB*) is only about
176 6% for the MMM [-1% to 13% across the models] (Table 2). Figure 5 (top) shows that the peak
177 seasonal DMAX8hrO₃ projections change slightly within the simulation period, with interannual
178 variability often exceeding the systematic trends. Under SSP1-2.6, the peak season
179 concentrations decrease by 17 µg m⁻³ (-20%) from 90 µg m⁻³ in 2015-2025 to 72 µg m⁻³ in 2041-
180 2050, while under SSP2-4.5, the decrease is 4 µg m⁻³ (-3%). On the other hand, under SSP3-7.0,
181 there is a slight increase of 2 µg m⁻³ (+2%). Under SSP1-2.6, where there is an overall decrease
182 across the domain, O₃ concentrations increase slightly over the Benelux region and Po valley,
183 which are the known hot spots (Figure 2, lower panel). The largest increases are projected to take
184 place over central Europe under SSP2-4.5, and over most of the study domain under SSP3-7.0.
185 EU countries on average are not projected to comply with the WHO guideline target value of 60
186 µg m⁻³ by 2050 under any of the emission scenarios. On the other hand, the first interim target of
187 100 µg m⁻³ can be achieved after 2035.

188

189 While the models suggest that achieving the peak seasonal target value for long-term exposure to
190 O₃ will not be possible by 2050, the annual 99th percentile target value of 100 µg m⁻³ (short-term
191 exposure) might be achieved by some countries under the SSP1-2.6 scenario, according to some
192 models (Figure 5 bottom).

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198 Figure 5. Top panel: Peak season surface daily maximum 8 hour O_3 (DMAX8hr O_3); bottom
199 panel: annual 99th percentile of DMAX8hr O_3 concentrations as simulated by the ensemble mean
200 in 2015-2050, averaged over EU member countries under different emission scenarios. The black
201 lines show the WHO guidelines target values of $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. Shaded
202 areas show the standard deviation between the individual models.

203 Compliance with the WHO guidelines in the individual EU countries are presented in Figure 6.
204 As seen in the figure, the ensemble-mean projects no compliance to the target long-term
205 exposure value of $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ among the EU countries under any of the emission scenarios, with
206 only 9 countries projected to reach the target after 2040 under the minimum model simulations.
207 On the other hand, the interim 1 value of $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ is achieved in SSP2-4.5 in all countries. The

208 interim 2 value of $70 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ is achieved in 21 countries in SSP1-2.6, and in 15 western and
 209 northern European countries in SSP2-4.5. On the other hand, Finland and Sweden will be able to
 210 comply with the short-term exposure value of $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ under SSP2-4.5, while more than half
 211 of the countries will comply with this threshold under the SSP1-2.6 scenario. These results imply
 212 that the short term O_3 exposure (8-hour) can be mitigated by emission reductions, particularly
 213 with ambitious reductions, whereas the long-term exposure will be more challenging for Europe.
 214 Particularly under the worst case scenario (SSP3-7.0), compliance to the new WHO target, and
 215 interim values are not possible in any European country. Similar to the compliance to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$,
 216 meeting the O_3 target and interim values will be particularly challenging in southern European
 217 countries due to much higher O_3 levels because of higher photochemical activity, UV radiation,
 218 and precursor sources [22].
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222
 223 Figure 6. WHO guidelines interim and target values (color coded) for long-term exposure (top

224 panel) and short-term exposure (bottom panel) to O₃ concentrations along with the compliance
225 across the EU member countries under SSP1-2.6 (right panel), SSP2-4.5 (middle panel), and
226 SSP3-7.0 (left panel). Target (Min) is based on the minimum values from three models, and all
227 the rest are based on the MMM.

228
229 In conclusion, complying with the new WHO air quality guidelines for PM_{2.5} and O₃ will be
230 challenging for several European countries in the near-term future until 2050. Our multi-model
231 ensemble of state-of-the-art regional atmospheric chemistry-transport models, using several
232 emission scenarios, and bias-correction for PM_{2.5}, shows that it requires ambitious emission
233 mitigations (e.g. SSP1-2.6) to achieve the WHO target value. Under moderate mitigation
234 scenarios (e.g. SSP2-4.5), only a few countries, and mainly only after the 2030s, can comply
235 with the PM_{2.5} target value. This challenge is partly associated with the fact that the natural
236 contribution from mineral dust and sea-salt can comprise up to 70% of the PM_{2.5}, which cannot
237 be mitigated. It should be noted that while there are indications from epidemiological and
238 experimental studies that desert dust can aggravate respiratory and potentially also
239 cardiovascular health, its effects may differ in magnitude and mechanism from those of urban
240 PM_{2.5} [23,24]. Our analyses show that the O₃ target value is practically unreachable before 2050.

241 242 **Discussion**

243
244 With its new EU directive on air quality in 2024, the EU set an ambitious roadmap, within which
245 air pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to human health. Even though our
246 results show that Europe will not be able to comply with the new WHO guidelines for PM_{2.5} and
247 O₃ unless extremely ambitious emission reductions take place, it is still beneficial to reduce
248 anthropogenic emissions to reduce air pollution and its negative health impacts. To show this, we
249 have calculated the percentage of the population of each country that is exposed to PM_{2.5}
250 concentrations above the new WHO guideline in 2015 and 2050 (Figure 7). On average, 94% of
251 the 2015 European population is exposed to PM_{2.5} concentrations above 5 µg m⁻³, while
252 projections show that in 2050, under SSP1-2.6, exposure to above 5 µg m⁻³ drops to 45% of the
253 population. Under SSP2-4.5 and SSP3-7.0, it falls by 2-5%, to 89% and 92%, respectively.
254 However, the change in the population fraction not exposed to concentrations above the target
255 limits strongly depends on the country. In some countries such as Denmark, Estonia, Finland,
256 Poland, Sweden, and Switzerland, large increases in the low-exposure population fraction are
257 achieved under all SSPs, by more than 20%. In most of the other countries, such increases are by
258 only a few percent under SSP2-4.5 and SSP3-7.0. These reductions in exposure will however
259 still avoid premature mortality and morbidity, leading to reductions in associated costs for the
260 society, and therefore are beneficial.

261

262
 263 Figure 7. Percentage of population exposed to surface PM_{2.5} levels over the WHO target value of
 264 5 µg m⁻³ in 2015, and in 2050 under different SSPs.

265
 266 Our results indicate that fulfilling WHO AQ recommendations requires mitigation strategies that
 267 introduce strong policies, fast renewable adoption, reduced consumption, widespread
 268 electrification in transport and industry, and global cooperation and coordination, leading to deep
 269 emissions cuts, following the SSP1-2.6 scenario. Continued reliance on fossil fuels and weaker
 270 carbon reduction policies than in SSP1-2.6, such as in SSP2-4.5, will lead to not fulfilling these
 271 recommendations.

272
 273 The above analysis took 2015 as the starting year for emission scenarios. One has to keep in
 274 mind that during the period of 2015-2024 the global emissions followed the SSP3-7.0 trend
 275 (Figure 8), i.e., the obtained results should be considered as optimistic. One should also note that
 276 the natural contribution to PM_{2.5} can be up to more than 50% in some countries, which would
 277 require even more drastic emission reductions to comply with the guidelines.

278
 279 A strength of our approach is the use of multiple atmospheric chemistry models and bias
 280 correction to simulate surface concentrations as close to the observed concentrations as possible.
 281 On the other hand, it also highlights the differences across models in their physical and chemical
 282 mechanisms and thus representation of atmospheric chemistry, aerosol processes, and natural

283 emissions, as summarized in Methods section 4 and Table S1. Therefore, our results advocate the
284 use of a suite of models for more robust policy recommendations.

285 **Methods**

286

287 **3. Climate Downscaling with WRF**

288 The WRF model version 4.1 [25] has been used for downscaling global climate scenarios. In this
289 study, the model domain has been set up with a 20 km horizontal resolution in a Polar
290 stereographic projection centered on 60N, and up to 10 hPa with 54 vertical layers. The study
291 domain covers continental Europe at 25-72N, 25W-45E.

292

293 Meteorological initial and boundary conditions to WRF are provided by the NCAR CESM2
294 model, which has a spatial resolution of 0.9x1.25 degree. This resolution is not sufficient to
295 resolve the highly variable air pollution concentrations within cities and countries. Boundary
296 conditions of 3-D temperature, humidity, horizontal winds and geopotential height are updated
297 every 6 hours in WRF, while sea surface temperatures and sea ice are updated daily. In the
298 present study, we have used future scenarios from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
299 Phase 6 (CMIP6: [26]), which feeds to the recent IPCC 6th Assessment Report (AR6). Three
300 shared socio-economic pathways (SSP) scenarios are used: SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5 and SSP3-7.0, to
301 address different levels of mitigation and adaptation [27]. SSP1 and SSP3 define various
302 combinations of high or low socio-economic challenges to climate change adaptation and
303 mitigation, while SSP2 describes medium challenges of both kinds and is intended to represent a
304 future in which development trends are not extreme in any of the dimensions, but rather follow
305 middle-of-the-road pathways [27]. The SSP1-2.6 scenario aims to achieve a 2100 radiative
306 forcing level of 2.6 W m⁻², keeping the temperature increase below 2 °C compared to the
307 preindustrial levels. The SSP2-4.5 describes a “middle of the road” socio-economic family with
308 a 4.5 W m⁻² radiative forcing level by 2100. The SSP3-7.0 scenario is a medium-high reference
309 scenario with the highest CO₂, methane and air pollution precursor emissions among the three
310 scenarios used in the present study.

311

312 In the present study, we use three state-of-the-art atmospheric chemistry and transport models to
313 simulate the surface PM_{2.5} and O₃ concentrations in the period of 2015 to 2050 over Europe
314 under different emission scenarios to assess the compliance of European countries to the new
315 WHO target and interim values. The emission scenarios are referred to as taking “the green road”
316 (SSP1-2.6), “the middle of the road” (SSP2-4.5) and “a rocky road” (SSP3-7.0). We also discuss
317 the implications on the population exposure to these pollutants.

318

319 4. Air Pollution Downscaling

320

321 We have used three state-of-the-art chemistry transport models: the Danish Eulerian
322 Hemispheric Model (DEHM), the System for Integrated modeLLing of Atmospheric coMposition
323 (SILAM), and the Weather Research and Forecasting model with chemistry (WRF-Chem).
324 DEHM and SILAM are members of the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS)
325 regional forecasting ensemble (<https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/regional-services>), providing
326 regional forecasts and analysis of air pollution over Europe. Fire emissions in all models are
327 produced by the Fire Forecasting Model, an extension of the IS4FIRES system [28]. The
328 physical, chemical, and aerosol mechanisms used in the models, along with their treatment of
329 natural aerosols and precursor gases are provided in Table S1.

330 The DEHM model was originally developed mainly to study the transport of SO₂ and sulfate
331 (SO₄) to the Arctic [29] and has been extended to different applications during the last decades.
332 It has been documented extensively [30] and evaluated in several intercomparison studies
333 [2,21,31-33]. The DEHM version used in the present study has a 20 km×20 km spatial resolution
334 over Europe, extending up to 100 hPa through 29 vertical levels, with the first layer height of
335 approximately 20 m. The gas-phase chemistry module includes 71 chemical species, 9 primary
336 particles, including natural particles such as sea-salt and 122 chemical reactions (Brandt et al.,
337 2012). The current version of the DEHM model does not include wind-blown or re-suspended
338 dust emissions (Table S1).

339 SILAM (<http://silam.fmi.fi>, [34]) version 5.8 is used both for the global boundary runs in 2
340 degree resolution and for the regional European runs with 0.4 × 0.3 degree resolution
341 (approximately 30 km). The global setup extends up to 3.7 hPa with 26 vertical layers. For
342 regional runs the lowest 19 layers from the global setup are used, the top being at 106 hPa.
343 Boundaries for these regional runs are taken from the global runs, updated every 3 hours. The
344 chemistry and aerosol mechanisms used in the SILAM model is provided in Table S1.

345

346 WRF-Chem [35] version 3.9.1.1 has been set up for a European domain at 35 km x 35 km
347 horizontal resolution and 50 vertical layers, ranging from the surface and up to 50 hPa. The
348 chemistry is online with the meteorology, and both direct and indirect (i.e., activation as cloud
349 droplets) aerosol feedback is accounted for. Simulations are run as multiple 15-month time slices
350 whereof the first 3 months (Oct-Dec) of each run are considered spin-up. Meteorological
351 boundary conditions from CESM2 were updated every 6 hours and spectral nudging towards the
352 global data was applied in the free troposphere (i.e., above the planetary boundary layer) for
353 temperature, horizontal winds, and geopotential height. Chemical boundary conditions are from
354 the global SILAM simulations.

355

356 The global SILAM runs that are used for boundary conditions for European regional runs have
357 been conducted at a spatial resolution of 2x2 degrees and with a temporal resolution (averaging

358 time window) of 3 hours. For the ERA5 meteorology, they cover a time window of 1980-2019.
359 For the CESM meteorology the historical part covers the years from mid-1940's to 2014.
360 However, the project interest is mainly in the time window of 1980-2014, which will be used for
361 the regional runs. All the three future scenario runs (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0, 4 TB per
362 scenario was stored for long term usage) cover the time window of 2015-2099.

363
364 The global runs have been conducted using the original (with a resolution of 0.5 degree) CMIP6
365 emissions for anthropogenic emissions [36]. They are complemented with NO_x emissions from
366 lightnings and MEGAN-MACC/CAMSv3.1 biogenic emissions [37], together with halogen
367 emissions based on the GEIA emission inventory and available data from the literature for yearly
368 changes of different CFC-compounds. Additionally, the emissions of N₂O from soils, together
369 with anthropogenic N₂O emissions from the EDGAR 5.0 inventory is included in simulations
370 (<https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>, [38]). For future SSP scenarios these anthropogenic N₂O
371 emissions are scaled with the different SSP scenario total emissions. For anthropogenic PM
372 coarse emissions, which are not available in the CMIP6 emissions inventories, we used the
373 EDGAR v4.3.2 emission inventory for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} to make the coarse PM. The future
374 development of PM coarse emission is estimated sector-wise from the development of CO and
375 NO_x emissions for different SSPs.

376

377 **5. Emissions**

378

379 The standard anthropogenic emissions are based on CMIP6 emissions at 0.5x0.5° resolution.
380 Historical emission inventory is CEDS inventory [36] and the future scenario emissions of
381 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs: [27]) are by Gidden et al. [39]. Figure 8 shows the
382 global CO₂ emissions in the different SSP scenarios [40] we have used in the present study,
383 along with the reported global CO₂ emissions by the Global Carbon Budget
384 (<https://globalcarbonbudget.org/>). These emissions are directly used in SILAM global
385 simulations. In regional (European scale) runs these emissions are remapped into 0.1x0.1 degree
386 grid cells by using the CAMS-GLOB-ANT emission inventory version 2.1 for year 2015 as a
387 proxy inside each 0.5x0.5 degree grid cell. If no emissions exist in CAMS inventory, a unity
388 profile is used inside the original CMIP6 grid cell. Aviation emissions are not regridded into
389 finer grids. Figure 9 shows the NO_x emissions from the transportation sector in 2015 and 2050 in
390 the original SSP2-4.5 scenario and its downscaled version used in this study.

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394

395 Figure 8. Reported and projected (SSPs: [40]) global CO₂ emissions. Reported CO₂ emissions396 are taken from the Global Carbon Budget (<https://globalcarbonbudget.org/>) under397 <https://ourworldindata.org/co2-emissions>. SSP are taken from398 [https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-](https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5)399 [scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-](https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5)400 [+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5](https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5)

401

402

403
 404 Figure 9. NO_x emissions from the transport sector in 2015 (upper panel) and 2050 (lower panel)
 405 as in CMIP6 emissions (SSP2-4.5: left panel) and downscaled in the present study (right panel).
 406

407 6. Model evaluation

408 All models that participated in the study have been extensively evaluated in numerous research
 409 and operational projects [2,28,41-44]. In addition to the existing evaluations, a dedicated effort
 410 has been made to quantify the uncertainties of the setup used in this study. Surface O₃ and PM_{2.5}
 411 measurements are taken from the EBAS database (<https://ebas.nilu.no/>) for the period 1980-
 412 2014. Model simulations are interpolated to observational stations using the nearest-grid
 413 interpolation. Only hourly measurements are used for O₃ evaluation and both hourly and daily
 414 measurements are used for PM_{2.5} evaluations. The DMAX8hrO₃ concentrations are calculated as
 415 the daily maximum of 8-hours moving average of hourly O₃ observations and only keep the data
 416 that have at least 6 hours in each 8 hours window. Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations are
 417 calculated from daily mean concentrations, and during each aggregation process, we use only
 418 measurements with 75% data availability for the time window. The evaluations metrics are
 419 calculated using these aggregated concentrations from all stations. As a result, DMAX8hrO₃
 420 concentrations are overestimated by up to 13%, with *r* values around 0.4-0.5 (Table 1). The time
 421 series of observed and modelled surface annual PM_{2.5} and DMAX8hrO₃ are presented in Figures
 422 S2 and S3, respectively. The multi-model ensemble-mean overestimates DMAX8hrO₃
 423 concentrations by 6%, with *r* values around 0.5. The models were less successful for surface

424 PM_{2.5} concentrations. All models underestimated annual mean surface PM_{2.5} by up to 57%, with
 425 the DEHM model having the largest underestimation. The Pearson correlation of annual mean
 426 PM_{2.5} is also around 0.4-0.5.

427
 428 Table 1. Mean bias (*MB*), root mean square error (*RMSE*), normalized mean bias (*NMB*),
 429 fractional gross error (*FGE*), Pearson correlation (*r*), and the regression coefficient (*r*²) for
 430 simulated daily maximum 8-hour moving average O₃ concentration (D_{MAX}8hrO₃) and annual
 431 mean PM_{2.5} concentrations against EBAS measurements in the 1980-2014 period for each model
 432 and their ensemble mean

433
 434

<i>Model</i>	<i>MB</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>NMB</i>	<i>FGE</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²
PM _{2.5} (Annual mean)						
DEHM	-5,17	6,70	-0,57	0,60	0,51	0,26
WRF-Chem	-0,86	4,55	-0,04	0,30	0,41	0,17
SILAM	-3,21	5,14	-0,32	0,38	0,53	0,28
EnsMean	-2,64	4,88	-0,24	0,33	0,50	0,25
O ₃ (D _{MAX} 8hrO ₃)						
DEHM	-0,30	25,98	0,03	0,27	0,52	0,27
WRF-Chem	-3,11	27,36	-0,01	0,29	0,42	0,18
SILAM	9,31	31,15	0,13	0,32	0,40	0,16
EnsMean	2,18	26,08	0,06	0,27	0,48	0,23

435
 436 These differences among models are due to several reasons including the different chemical
 437 mechanisms, which leads to differences in simulated O₃ concentrations, different aerosol
 438 mechanisms leading to differences in size distribution and secondary aerosol formation ,
 439 native model spatial and vertical resolutions that lead to differences in transport as well as dry
 440 and wet removal in the atmosphere, and inclusion and simulation of natural aerosols, as
 441 described in the Methods section 4 and presented in Table S1. For example, the largest biases of
 442 the DEHM model with respect to PM_{2.5} levels compared to other models are partly because the
 443 DEHM model does not include mineral dust, which can be quite important in southern Europe.
 444 The spatial and temporal breakdown of errors in these models have been analyzed in previous
 445 work [32].

446
447 In addition, models do not capture the temporal evolution of the observed concentrations because
448 the CESM2 climate model has been run without nudging, and therefore creates its own
449 meteorology, which can largely deviate from the true meteorology. Therefore, it is not expected
450 to obtain good statistics using CESM2-driven models for short time scales.

451 452 **7. Bias correction**

453
454 In the present study, we bias-corrected surface PM_{2.5} concentrations due to large
455 underestimations and large uncertainties in the aerosol chemistry caused by physical (e.g. size
456 distribution) and chemical (e.g. chemical composition) properties in the different models. On the
457 other hand, surface O₃ concentrations were used as calculated by the models without any
458 correction, as the biases here are considerably smaller across all models (Table 1) and bias
459 correction did not result in substantial improvement.

460
461 For PM_{2.5}, a gridded satellite-derived dataset [45] was used as observational reference for the
462 correction, meaning we try to minimize any model biases relative to this dataset. It consists of
463 global monthly mean concentrations from 1998 to 2022 at a horizontal resolution of 0.1°x 0.1°,
464 and combines measurements from multiple satellites (specifically MODIS, VIIRS, MISR, and
465 SeaWiFS) with the GEOS-Chem chemical transport model and a Convolutional Neural Network
466 for calibration to surface observations. Due to a lack of availability of high-quality gridded PM_{2.5}
467 observations at daily resolution, we decided to estimate bias correction parameters on monthly
468 scales and then apply them to the respective daily projections. The 1998-2014 period was
469 selected for parameter estimation (coinciding with the end of historical model simulations), and
470 these parameters were then applied to simulations from the periods 1980-1997 and 2015-2050
471 (all emission scenarios). The remaining 2015-2022 reference data was used for out-of-sample
472 evaluation of the bias corrected projections (see Figure 10).

473 Due to its versatility and ability to preserve long-term model trends, we chose the quantile delta
474 mapping bias correction method (QDM; [46]), which removes biases by adjusting multiple
475 quantiles and thereby addresses the entire distribution as compared to just and/or variance.
476 We here use the version implemented in the R software package MBC [47]. In a first step,
477 quantiles from the empirical distribution function of future projections are detrended with respect
478 to the quantiles of the historical/estimation period, which yields the model trend Δ as the ratio
479 between the future and historical quantiles. Next, the detrended quantiles are bias-corrected by
480 mapping them onto the respective quantiles from the reference dataset (regular quantile
481 mapping). Finally, we obtain bias-corrected future projections by re-applying the model trend Δ
482 to the bias-corrected quantiles from the previous step through multiplication. This method was
483 applied to all three models on a grid-point-wise basis and using n equidistant quantiles, where n
484 is the total amount of time points in the future period. The QDM approach explicitly preserves
485 long-term trends (whereas they can deteriorate significantly when using regular quantile

486 mapping) and presents a suitable option for bias-correction atmospheric variables lacking
 487 specialized techniques, in particular when models can be expected to represent future trends in a
 488 realistic manner.

489
 490 In Figure 10, we show mean bias (*MB*) and root-mean-square error (*RMSE*) for historical and
 491 future model projections, based on comparison against the EBAS ground-based observations.
 492 The evaluations are conducted for monthly mean PM_{2.5} values at all measurement stations. We
 493 only keep data with 75% availability during the process and use the nearest-grid interpolation for
 494 model simulations. In most instances, model skill has improved with bias correction, in particular
 495 for the DEHM model, which moved from a considerable negative bias to a slightly positive one.
 496 Of course, any bias correction approach relies heavily on the quality and accuracy of the
 497 reference data set, which can be a particular challenge for air pollution variables. In addition,
 498 Figure S4 shows the time series of monthly mean observed PM_{2.5} along with simulated
 499 concentrations before and after bias correction.

500

Scenario	Model	MB		RMSE	
		before BC	after BC	before BC	after BC
CESM (1980-2014)	DEHM	-5.0	1.2	8.0	6.5
	WRF-Chem	-0.9	1.7	7.0	7.1
	SILAM	-3.1	1.7	7.1	6.6
ssp126 (2015-2022)	DEHM	-3.5	0.8	5.3	4.5
	WRF-Chem	0.02	1.8	4.7	4.8
	SILAM	-2.0	0.7	4.9	4.7
ssp245 (2015-2022)	DEHM	-3.5	0.8	5.3	4.3
	WRF-Chem	0.3	2.2	4.8	5.0
	SILAM	-1.9	1.2	5.0	4.8
ssp370 (2015-2022)	DEHM	-3.1	1.8	5.0	4.9
	WRF-Chem	0.8	3.1	4.9	5.9
	SILAM	-1.5	2.2	4.9	5.4

501
 502 Figure 10. Mean bias (*MB*) and root mean square error (*RMSE*) for surface PM_{2.5} in the
 503 individual models before and after bias correction. Bold numbers indicate improvements in
 504 accuracy.

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714

715 Figure 1. Bias-corrected surface PM_{2.5} concentrations as predicted by the ensemble mean in
716 2015-2050 over continental Europe under different emission scenarios (solid lines of the
717 corresponding color). The black line shows the WHO guidelines target value of 5 µg m⁻³. Shaded
718 ranges show the standard deviation between the individual models.

719
720 Figure 2. PM_{2.5} (upper panel) and O₃ (lower panel) surface concentrations in 2050 with respect to
721 2015 under different emissions scenarios: SSP3-7.0 (left panel), SSP2-4.5 (middle panel), and
722 SSP1-2.6 (right panel).

723
724 Figure 3. WHO interim and target values for surface PM_{2.5} and the compliance across European
725 countries under SSP1-2.6 (right panel), SSP2-4.5 (middle panel), and SSP3-7.0 (left panel).

726
727 Figure 4. Primary natural (mineral dust and sea-salt) contribution (%) to domain-mean PM_{2.5}
728 mass over Europe in SILAM (upper left panel) and WRF-Chem (upper right panel) under
729 different SSP scenarios (shaded areas represent the spatial variability). Lower panels show 2015
730 annual mean of the dust + sea-salt contribution (%) to PM_{2.5} under SSP2-4.5 scenario for SILAM
731 (left) and WRF-Chem (right). The dot-shaded regions are where PM_{2.5} concentrations are above
732 5 µg m⁻³.

733
734 Figure 5. Top panel: Peak season surface daily maximum 8 hour O₃ (D_{MAX8hrO₃}); bottom
735 panel: annual 99th percentile of D_{MAX8hrO₃} concentrations as simulated by the ensemble mean
736 in 2015-2050, averaged over EU member countries under different emission scenarios. The black
737 lines show the WHO guidelines target values of 60 µg m⁻³ and 100 µg m⁻³, respectively. Shaded
738 areas show the standard deviation between the individual models.

739
740 Figure 6. WHO guidelines interim and target values (color coded) for long-term exposure (top
741 panel) and short-term exposure (bottom panel) to O₃ concentrations along with the compliance
742 across the EU member countries under SSP1-2.6 (right panel), SSP2-4.5 (middle panel), and
743 SSP3-7.0 (left panel). Target (Min) is based on the minimum values from three models, and all
744 the rest are based on the MMM.

745
746 Figure 7. Percentage of population exposed to surface PM_{2.5} levels over the WHO target value of
747 5 µg m⁻³ in 2015, and in 2050 under different SSPs.

748
749 Figure 8. Reported and projected (SSPs: [40]) global CO₂ emissions. Reported CO₂ emissions
750 are taken from the Global Carbon Budget (<https://globalcarbonbudget.org/>) under
751 <https://ourworldindata.org/co2-emissions>. SSP are taken from
752 [https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-](https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5)
753 [scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-](https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5)
754 [+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5](https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/ipcc-scenarios?Metric=Greenhouse+gas+emissions&Rate=Total&Region=Global&country=SSP3+-+Baseline~SSP1+-+2.6~SSP2+-+4.5)

755 Figure 9. NO_x emissions from the transport sector in 2015 (upper panel) and 2050 (lower panel)
756 as in CMIP6 emissions (SSP2-4.5: left panel) and downscaled in the present study (right panel).

757

758 Figure 10. Mean bias (*MB*) and root mean square error (*RMSE*) for surface PM_{2.5} in the
759 individual models before and after bias correction. Bold numbers indicate improvements in
760 accuracy.

761

762

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772

773 **Contributions**

774

775 UI developed the manuscript, UI, ZY, JHC, CG and JB performed and analyzed DEHM
776 simulations, RH and MS performed and analyzed SILAM simulations, LM and ØH performed
777 and analyzed WRF-Chem simulations, NS performed the bias-correction, and ZY performed grid
778 transformations and model evaluation. SC calculated the healthy population estimates. All
779 authors provided content and editing.